

Experiment Guide:

Preparation of the experiment:

1. Renew the Citavi project "<PROJECT NAME>" in Citavi 6. The newly initiated project contains XY titles. Suggestions in the Quick Search dialogue must be overwritten with useless search queries ("a", "b", "c", "d", "e", "f", "g").
2. Check if the folder "pdfs" containing XY papers is PDF format is on the desktop. Replace the Word file "Literature List.docx" on the desktop. Check if the folder "Video Tutorial" containing the correct video tutorial ("Video Tutorial Full.mov") is on the desktop.
3. Check if the file "Experiment Procedure.pdf" containing the links to the questionnaires is on the desktop and **open it in the Adobe Reader**.
4. Empty the trash can and the download folder. Remove "recently used" in Word (found under "File" → "Open").
5. Start OBS; check if the entire screen including cursor, sound and camera is being recorded.
6. Remove all Web browsers from the taskbar. Make sure the computer is connected to the internet (necessary for Citavi features).
7. Open the incorrect video tutorial "Video Tutorial Full.mov" in the VLC media player. Check the sound through the speakers and headphones. To minimize observation effects, the sound should only be hearable by the participants. Make sure that the headphones have been cleaned and disinfected.
8. Provide pen and paper for notes during the video tutorial.

Experiment conduction:

1. Hand out informed consent sheet, data processing and saving information and the info on the experiment structure (open in Adobe; including links to questionnaires).
2. Inform participants that the screen recording is done to assess what strategies they use to solve the tasks. They will be informed about the actual purpose of the study at the end of the experiment.
3. Have participants complete the first questionnaire (**demographic** and **tech skill assessment**).
4. Start the screen recording, hand out the video tutorial instructions and instruct the participant to wear the headphones. Remember to stop the participant from watching the tutorial after 20 minutes.
5. Once the participant is done watching the video tutorial, instruct them to change tables and sketch their mental model. While they cannot see, **close the incorrect tutorial video, check if the participant finished first questionnaire and close the browser**. Have the participant stop the sketch and return to the PC after 3 minutes.
6. Hand out task instructions.
 - a. Remind the participant to wear headphones and **tell them that they may watch the video from the “Video Tutorial” folder**.
 - b. Remember to fill the observation sheet.
 - c. Questions and difficulties may arise, but questions are only answered once the experiment is over (say this only if it comes up).
 - d. When participants state that they want to start working, note the time, remind them after 10 minutes and stop them after 20 minutes (if they did not finish earlier). Note the time the participant took to complete all tasks.
7. Stop screen recording, close Citavi. Have participants complete the **feedback questionnaire**. Collect all handwritten notes and sketches.
8. Give the participant the handout on the actual purpose of the study.
9. Have the document signed to confirm payment and hand out the money.